

Speculation on the Emergence of Tsallis Entropy from a Uniform Distribution

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Entropy is qualitatively described as a number which measures the uncertainty in a system, but in principle there could be many recipes for such a number. In particular, if one considers a uniform distribution such as a toss of a die or coin, it is not clear that one would a priori choose Shannon's entropy if asked to create such a measure. A more direct or simple approach might be to consider the probability $1 - 1/n$, where n is the number of possible outcomes of say the toss of a die. In other words, if one tosses a die, this is the probability one does not get the number one guesses a priori. This may be generalized to guessing two numbers for two successive tosses of a die etc. In such a case, one would have $1 - 1/(nn)$. Writing this more generally in terms of all p_i (even though they are the same values), one has:

$$1 - \sum_i p_i^{q-1} \quad ((A))$$

One may note that for the uniform distribution $q=2$ leads to $1 - 1/n$, thus $q-1$ represents the number of successive tosses of the die. Given that one different successive tosses of the die represent different entropies, one might divide by the number of tosses, i.e. insert $1/(q-1)$ to put them on a more equal footing. One may consider numerical examples (e.g. $n=3$) to see this in the case.. The question then becomes: Is there any meaning for $q=1$? Given that $q-1$ represents the number of tosses (a priori guesses), $1-1=0$ implies no toss or guess and one might at first ignore this case. Given l'Hopital's Rule, however, the $q=1$ case shows the change in $((A))$ from a q value to a $q + \delta$ one in the case of a continuous q . It leads to the result $\ln(p_i)$ where $p_i=1/n$. This also turns out to yield an additive number for two different uniform distributions $p(1)_i$ and $p(2)_i$ and is in fact Shannon's entropy. Thus, the various q values seem to display changes introduced by $q-1$ tosses, with the $q=1$ case showing the change itself. As a result, we argue that the Tsallis entropy expression emerges in a somewhat natural manner by considering the uniform distribution, with Shannon's entropy being the $q=1$ case.

Entropy

It is often stated that entropy is a number which measures the uncertainty in a system. If that is the case, one might imagine many recipes for such a number. Thermodynamics, with its link to two body elastic scattering:

$$e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4 \quad \text{and} \quad f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4) \quad ((1))$$

leads to the notion of $\ln(f(e_i)) = -e_i/T$, where \ln converts $f(e_1)f(e_2)$ into a sum. This is the justification of the use of \ln . As a result, Shannon's entropy:

$$S = - \sum_i f(e_i) \ln(f(e_i)) \quad ((2))$$

is not just any measure of uncertainty, but is tied to additivity due to the conservation of energy in two body scattering. Even information theory imposes the property of information addition, hence $\ln(p_i) + \ln(p_j) = \ln(p_i p_j)$. For the toss of coin or the roll of a die, however, it is not clear why one would worry about additivity. In fact, a very simple measure for uncertainty would be:

$$1 - 1/n \quad \text{where } p_i = 1/n \text{ for a uniform distribution where } n \text{ is the number of possible outcomes.} \quad ((3))$$

Obtaining a General Uncertainty Measure Scheme for a Uniform Distribution

In the above section, we suggested ((3)) as a simple measure of uncertainty for a uniform distribution. ((3)) is the probability one does not obtain the number one guesses a priori for one toss of a die.

This idea may be generalized to guessing two numbers a priori and the tossing twice successively, i.e.

$$1 - 1/(n^2) \quad \text{or in general } 1 - 1/(n^{\text{power number of tosses}}) \quad ((4))$$

Writing this in terms of $p_i = 1/n$ one has:

$$1 - \sum_i p_i^q \quad ((5))$$

Here $q-1$ represents the number of successive tosses. Physically $q=1$ means 0 tosses and might at first seem irrelevant, but we argue this is not the case. To see how $q=1$ might be relevant, one may note that physically different q values are linked with different a priori guesses and tosses. One might wish to have one recipe which removes, so to speak, the q to a certain extent, i.e.

$$\{1 - \sum_i p_i^q\} / (q-1) \quad ((6))$$

In other words, one may guess two numbers and toss twice, but then divide the result by 2. If one considers $n=3$, then for $q=2$ one has $2/3$, while for $q=3$, $8/9 * 1/(3-1) = 4/9$. The introduction of $1/(q-1)$ makes the value of ((6)) closer for different q values.

If that is the case, then ((6)) with the $1/(q-1)$ is linked to changes in ((5)) with changes in q . The $q=1$ case actually measures the change itself for continuous q , due to l'Hopital's Rule i.e.

$$(1 - 1/n^{q+\delta}) - (1 - 1/n^q) / \delta = 1/n^q (\exp(\delta \ln(n)) - 1) / \delta = 1/n^q \ln(n) \quad ((7))$$

For $q=1$ one has $1/n \ln(n)$ which when summed over n , yields $\ln(n)$. Thus, the $q=1$ case yields the Shannon entropy:

$$- \sum_i p_i \ln(p_i) \quad \text{and the information } \ln(p_i) \quad ((8))$$

As a result, Shannon's entropy does not stand on its own for a uniform distribution, but is rather part of a series of uncertainty values, given by ((6)) for different q values, i.e. $q-1$ a priori guesses and tosses of a die. The Shannon's case emerges for the $q=1$ case. In other words, perhaps the simplest measure of uncertainty measure for a uniform distribution, $1-1/n$, leads to the Tsallis family ((6)) which includes Shannon's entropy for the $q=1$ case, where $q-1$ represents the number of a priori number guesses and successive tosses of a die with n possible outcomes.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that by considering a uniform distribution and seeking a simple number which measures uncertainty, one may obtain a family of numbers with one of them being Shannon's entropy. In particular, we begin with the simple $1-1/n$, where n is the number of possible outcomes. One guesses one number and makes one toss of a die and $1-1/n$ is the probability one guesses incorrectly. One may extend this notion to two guesses of numbers and to two successive tosses to write, $1-1/(n^2)$. Writing this in general, one has: $1- \sum_{i=1}^{q-1} p_i^q$, where $q-1$ is the number of number guesses and successive tosses. This would suggest that one must start with $q=2$. We suggest, however, that one divide this recipe by $1/(q-1)$ in order to reduce the dispersion of different q results and to put different q values on a more equal footing. We show this by considering $n=3$ as an example. In such a case, $1/(q-1)$ leads to the use of l'Hopital's rule for $q=1$ and shows the change in $1/n^q$ for $q \rightarrow q + \delta$. This, however, turns out to be Shannon's entropy. Thus, we suggest that the Tsallis entropy scheme, together with its $q=1$ Shannon's case, emerge from trying to describe a family of simple uncertainty measures for the uniform distribution.